

NEW SOCIALITIES AND NODAL POINTS: RECONSTRUCTING THE FABRIC

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¹¹¹ *Philotes (Love) and Neikos (Strife)*

Out of the pan into the fire

We should not be scared of the expression meaning that from a difficult or dangerous situation we jump to a worse one – the Italian equivalent is: “dalla padella nella brace” – though, to be honest, the generalized disaster is escalating with no visible possibility of recovery. It is because, writing about reconstruction, we necessarily have to refer to the “difficult or dangerous situations”, since reconstruction presupposes something that has already collapsed, it is a positivity that confronts and rises as resistance to a negativity.

Important is the preposition re- which means that the old is constructed anew, that a new structure replaces the worn and collapsed in the same form. It is therefore necessary to know what has been destroyed or altogether mutated into negativity, into something threatening, how and when this happened, as well as the interweaving of positivity and negativity, perhaps using new terms. There are, for example, the terms of emergence and morphogenesis, still vague and introduced in architectural culture in a very remote theoretical field. In architecture, the term reconstruction dominates, as an uncontradicted, almost moralistic, positivity. We must also necessarily distinguish reconstruction as an architectural practice that concerns historical objects, from its general use. But we must say, even

very briefly, that the destruction – which reconstruction presupposes – is teleological, natural, it resides inside the form and develops quietly in decay and aging, it is inherent in becoming, and there we will need other theoretical weapons to deal with it, even another logic, and certainly,

the terms emergence and morphogenesis. There seems to be an intrinsic historicity imprinted on things, the life, the death, the memory and the oblivion of forms, like a ripple, an “unconscious oeuvre” of nature, of the poetics of time. We will content ourselves with this brief comment, since Empedocles – Φιλότης and Νείκος¹ – are for most people very far from architecture.

Our direction in this text is not the historical object.

We will follow the path paved by Studio's team, the path of reconstruction as positivity, the reminiscence of the form, its duration.

Describing the present situation, we would say that we are at a turning point, and these turning points, like recoveries, are always long, generations live and die during them. So, for example, the Reconstruction, that we discuss now, could be seen as an objection to the Deconstruction of the early 90s, and on a level of analysis this would be legitimate and – most importantly – up to date.

Another example, which is more of a fact that we take into account, is that those born before 1945 experienced, even as infants, the war and the post-war cold stability literally as Reconstruction.

All the rest of us, those born after 1960 in particular (i.e. the generations trivially described as: X,Y,Z, Alpha ... Ω_mega!) are living – and some of us will die – in a transitional period, certainly intense with many fluctuations, which is a deep turning point with no possibility of recovery,

we believe, despite all the daily celebrations of popularized science, the euphoria and frivolity of (social -) media, the promises of technology, and the optimism of a new reconstructed life on the exoplanets.

For some years now we have been living its dramatic peak, or should we say its nadir. All the transitions have been completed: the mechanical and analogue have been completely assimilated into the digital that imposes its language and its logical acts, the physical material has faded into the virtual, the political has become geopolitical on a global level, and then mutated into bio-political, returning from the longitudes and latitudes of geography to the human subject and its formations, the economy of presence has been superseded and controlled by the operation of the network economy, production by the provision of services, the watermarked paper money has become invisible crypto. The thought from Apps. All that we mention superficially has a direct effect on the primary level of architecture, where, in the modern period at least, its mandate comes from: the individual and the formations of the human, relationships, 'society' in general, the social fabric and the institutions.

Deconstruction in the 1990s, with its tumultuous, intense geometry and the self-referentiality of architecture, exploded theory, but what it mainly – and politically – did was a radical act that foreshadowed and introduced us to the New World that was then beginning to emerge, in 1989, a landmark year with the fall of the Berlin Wall, marking at the same time the end of modernity.

Then, architectural offices called Labs, which within the frame of a digital formalism created organic ectopic forms, appeared in Western societies, where a school, a church, and a gym closed down, and in their place opened a biotechnology centre, an Alzheimer's clinic, and a laboratory for synthetic drugs.

Architectural programs – as we know them from the modern era – as formulations of the needs and character of societies have in turn been radically altered. The Museum, for example, which currently is flourishing, was born as a program sometime at the end of the 18th century and will soon die, taking the form of statistics in the era of the A.I.: the most used object will be historical. Simple, easy and fair!!

Of course, new innovations in science and technology allow human beings to extend their imagination and practical reach, but in general these transitions, a huge bio-political program, under the title Reforms, which was implemented at least in Europe – has left gaps and wounds: in societies, in the human reason, at the relationships and on the body.

We will try to see, with a concrete example in a cutting-edge society, the possibility of handling and a little bit of healing what the subcutaneous crisis and the slow but radical, up to the human mind and language, Reform leaves in the social body, without, however, demonizing the developments.

Out of the furnace into the Capitol

The weird, primitive, idle, well-fed, well-armed and well-informed political morpheme that invaded the Capitol is an indicative example of the

ALL THAT WE MENTION SUPERFICIALLY HAS A DIRECT EFFECT ON THE PRIMARY LEVEL OF ARCHITECTURE

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strangeness of the present situation in a cutting-edge society, meaning by this a powerful society that produces developments, technological, ideological, aesthetics, and influential foreign policy.

But in all advanced societies, especially those that have mutated through the Reforms, the same phenomenon is observed: deindustrialization had the consequence that a large percentage of the population can live on state allowances, which are channeled from the excess profits of the technology giants and the export activity of the industries which, however, have transferred their production, the physical labor, to areas with low labor costs,

or operate with immigrants who do not have the free time or the education to go to the Museum.

Essentially a large percentage of the population is inactive or underemployed and somehow marginalized, creating a society enclosed into the society.

It would not be an exaggeration to say that there is no longer such a sharp difference between rich and poor - forgive me for saying so, but almost

everyone in Africa or Latin America now has a beef steak or something similar on their plate.

The difference is between an idle, inert body and the ability to live satisfying all its needs. This is an invisible gap, a consequence of radical changes, complementary and underlying to the great gaps in the social fabric.

A sensitive 2013 film, *Out of the Furnace*, describes this situation very well: the de-industrialization and marginalization of the active population in the digital economy. It is about the enclosure of society to itself, a kind of ontological paralysis of a large part of society. It is about the paradoxical

**AT THIS LIMINAL AND CRITICAL POINT
THERE IS A NEED TO USE ALL THE ACTIVE
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*Mould NMA: National Museum of
Afghanistan_Mould*

impasse of being able to live relatively well - that is, having money for travel, drugs, lots of pizzas, and being able to satisfy all one's needs, especially sexual needs - without working, without going to the Museum, that is, without physical, social or intellectual labor.

New Socialities

Summarizing, and taking for granted that the state structures have nowadays a mediator role, at best a regulator, we would say that: in contemporary societies where the presence of the state is increasingly weakened and the institutions are gradually fading in the background, the danger of absolute disruption of relations, the disorientation, isolation and marginalization of a large part of the productive forces, is visible, already present. We think we have to deal with this - it's not about unemployment - at least try to handle it, to reverse the situation, to activate the social body that is in ontological paralysis. At this liminal and critical point there is a need to use all the active potentials, to try to Reconstruct the coherence of the system, to knit the fabric again.

We have already said that all innovations in science and technology have not only led to a problematic rearrangement of the social fabric, leaving gaps and traumas, but at the same time allow individuals to extend their imagination and practical reach. There is, at least as a possibility, a plethora of new directions in real-world sociality. We will make use of the term New Socialities as a tool that will help us to better understand - and perhaps express - the new dynamics and arrive at some form of them, their *mise en oeuvre*.

*HE: Houston Endowment
Headquarters_Concept01*

Fabric: Houston Endowment
Headquarters_Fabric03

Field: Houston Endowment
Headquarters_Field 03

Field: Houston Endowment
Headquarters_Field 04

The term has become increasingly prominent in sociocultural anthropology and social sciences over the last few decades, and has been used in a startlingly divergent number of ways. Attempting a definition, the term conceptualizes "a dynamic relational matrix within which subjects are constantly interacting in ways that are co-productive, and continually plastic and malleable"². Instead of the now static terms "society", "social relations", or the "social classes" i.e. the formal patterns of hierarchy, it is processual, focusing on the dynamic social process "in which any person is inevitably engaged, rather than a set of rules or customs or structures or even meanings, that exist as a system independently of the individual". It thus opens up to a diversity of relationships, to a multiplicity of subjects and to a multitude of new directions. It also opens to other types of sociality such as that of (or with) animals or of materials. The term as a tool - and the relevant literature - can be used, but there are some friction points, which we will briefly mention:

- The terminology used by the social sciences is very rigid and, of course, very political, imposing dipoles, dichotomies, and a binding morphology: observer and observed, narrator and consumer, pacts and bonds, manipulation and transformation of social actors; agents are missing, but believe me, they are there too!
- Instead of the term matrix, for reasons that we cannot develop here, we use the terms: mould, field, hub, magmas, nucleus,
- Our own analysis, which follows the path laid out by Cornelius Castoriadis³ already in the 1970s, is also dynamic enough and follows the procedure: magmas, ensidic logic, symbolic language. This natural process - for the rational human being and his formations with "others" - has clearly been altered and contaminated by the invasion of heterogeneous digital logic, of cybernetics, but fundamentally it remains exactly as it is and remains only to rediscover it. For us this would be the actual Reconstruction.
- The fact that "human sociality requires an explicit theory of human subjects" is under critical scrutiny in these bio-technological times we live in.

New nodal points

The positive case of Houston Endowment

I would like briefly to share with you my experience of designing the Headquarters of the Houston Endowment which is a private initiative, based in Houston - Texas, that funds projects of individuals and organizations fulfilling social functions. From its nature consists a nodal point, a hub, a convergence field and a common place where the potentialities of society are activated, mixed and interacting, creating new formations, new relationships, and new balances. The basic goal of this nodal point is to bridge the gap that separates non-privileged people from opportunities, to open up horizons and strengthen the coherence of society, supporting the institutions at the same time; to bring together groups of citizens and individuals who can contribute resources, groups and individuals in need

^[2] In "Sociality, New directions", edited by Nicholas J. Long and Henrietta L. Moore, Berghahn Books, 2013.

^[3] For us more a philosopher than a political thinker, if, of course, we could separate the two sides.

HE: Houston Endowment
Headquarters_Concept02Fabric: Houston Endowment
Headquarters_Fabric04

of support and activation, groups and individuals with ideas, groups and individuals with know-how and willingness to perform, and finally institutions that need empowerment from the bottom and wish active participation of citizens.

At this moment, the Endowment operates in the framework of history (=consciousness) and of art (= expression and interaction), but through our point of view, we could very well see the range of activities to expand in the domains of ecology (the climatic change and the unique ecosystem of the area), of cooperatives (products, crafts) and innovation.

Texas is an important spearhead in the global system, and Houston is a functional and privileged area, sufficiently sensitive to detect imbalances early on and to diagnose problems and solutions more clearly than in other parts of the globe; therefore, we could say that the presence and functioning of the Houston Endowment could be described even as paradigmatic or pioneering expressing well the need for nuclei that can guarantee the necessary coherence of the system.

The design

All these that we mentioned, which, in our opinion, form the character of the Houston Endowment, should be expressed in the headquarters building. The design challenges were many, we can refer to three.

First of all, the mix and difficult balance between groups with different roles and functions must be expressed. The balance between representative and everyday realities, formal and innovative, functional and expressive, open and closed, or as from the Houston Endowment itself has been formulated: "how to integrate the new-community-focused aspects of the project with the operational needs of the workspace environment" and how to define, both programmatically and morphologically, the engagement spaces.

In addition to this, the Houston Endowment headquarters building is not only private and not only public: it is a hybrid form where the - basically charitable - private initiative meets a heterogeneous, multilayered social substrate that seeks for a way to become productive and to express itself. On the boundary between all this, the nodal point is called to express

"new socialities" and, at the same time, to be defined by them. The second big design challenge has been raised from the overall image we have for the building as a Field, Hub, and Mould. Following this view, we are hardly dealing with a "conventional" building, but rather with a plexus of relationships and a set of uses, with more actions than functions. And there, there are no clear shapes, but the areas and the intensity of the encounter, the threads, the dynamics of the shapes and the manifold of the forms, that lead us to the creation of a field, the knitting of relationships, the coherence, the texture of the contact, the community and the common horizon.

The third design challenge is the relationship of the building to the immediate - and wider - urban fabric and environment and the relationship - connection to the park in the south. The site is extremely favorable for a special and privileged relationship with the city and the neighboring park due to the significant terrain slope. These two facts leave much room for the Houston Endowment Headquarter building to become a focal point and reference to the large network of parks and recreation in the wider urban area.

The diagrams we present do not display any kind of design proposal but rather is an intention to visualize the character we attach to the Houston Endowment, its function and its physical presence.

Field, Hub, and Mould.

It is essentially a generic scheme, in effect a mould, which includes all geometric solutions and possible choices: the forms can be rectangular, curved, compact or fragmentary, organic or prismatic.

The important thing is to show, in this first diagrammatic operation, that there is an underlying level, under the general syntax and geometry, a first

THERE ARE NO CLEAR SHAPES, BUT THE AREAS AND THE INTENSITY OF THE ENCOUNTER

Mould NMA: National Museum of
Afghanistan_Mould 03

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embossed map, which expresses what we have tried to say above: the mag-
mas of "new socialities", the plexus and the texture of relationships, the
potentialities, the field structure, the fluidity. This underlying map exists,
and it is the one that could attribute character to the building.

We proposed a spectral solution, this determining underlying map, actu-
ally the first terms of a field, in an open consultation- with the aim to
elaborate the final shape of the building together with the developer and
those who are involved in the project.

By way of a conclusion

The good news is that we can still discuss Reconstruction, that is, consider
the possibility of the human being to produce vital, for him and his chil-
dren, forms. And there, as architects, we have the expertise.
The bad news is that the Anthropocene is empty of human beings.
And there, as architects, we cannot do anything. Jakarta doesn't exist any-
more.